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ISOLATION AND MOLECULAR CHARACTERIZATION OF *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* FROM COMMERCIAL MILK (FURA) IN MAIDUGURI

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ABSTRACT

*The isolation and molecular characterization of bacteria are foundational for controlling and improving processes in industries such as dairy, ensuring product safety, quality, and innovation. This study was conducted to isolate and characterize *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* from commercial milk (fura) hawkers in Maiduguri. The sample was obtained locally from commercial milk (Fura) hawkers in Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria. The microbiological analysis of locally fermented milk (Fura) samples revealed that all isolates exhibited distinct colony morphologies and biochemical profiles. Colonies with creamy, shiny appearances were primarily identified as *Lactobacillus* spp., while whitish, round colonies were associated with *Streptococcus* spp. Biochemical tests showed that all isolates were positive for carbohydrate fermentation (lactose, maltose, glucose, sucrose, fructose) but negative for indole, citrate, urease, MR, and VP tests. Molecular analysis using PCR further confirmed the presence of *Streptococcus thermophilus* in three isolates, while eleven isolates were identified as *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*. The finding of this study aligned with previous research on lactic acid bacteria in traditional dairy products, though differences in bacterial profiles may stem from variations in fermentation methods and environmental conditions. Overall, the findings underscore the necessity of molecular testing for accurate bacterial identification in food production.*

Keywords: *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*; *Streptococcus thermophilus*; Isolation; Primer; Probiotics

INTRODUCTION

Probiotics are live microorganism bacteria or fungi which when consumed at appropriate quantity, confers a beneficial health effect on the host by promoting the growth and proliferation of beneficial bacteria in the digestive tract [1]. The discoveries on the advantages of these organisms have made an outstanding breakthrough in food as well as healthcare sectors [2]. Bacteria in the genera *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacteria*, *Bacillus*, *Pediococcus*, *Streptococcus* and some yeast meets the condition necessary for their suitability for use as probiotics which includes; Their total safety to the host, resistance to gastric acidity, bile salt, pancreatic secretions and enzymes activity, ability to adhere to colonic mucosa and epithelial cells, antimicrobial activity, tolerance to food additives and ability to maintain viability during storage [3].

Lactobacillus bulgaricus and *Streptococcus thermophilus* are pivotal in the dairy industry for yogurt production due to their ability to ferment lactose into lactic acid, which imparts texture and flavor to yoghurt [4]. Their proper isolation and characterization ensure quality control in fermentation processes and contribute to the development of probiotic products that benefit gut health. Understanding these microorganisms at a molecular level also supports their use in other industrial applications, including the production of other fermented foods and biotechnological products.

Increased use of non-nutritive sweeteners, antimicrobial and preservative agents in production of many finished products may constitute a potential health hazard to consumers of such products. Moreover, maintaining viability of starter cultures during storage, sensory properties, shelflife and physicochemical properties of many finished products like yoghurt is a major challenge to producers of these products. Therefore, a potential symbiotic product (bioactive yoghurt) constituting honey as a (natural sweetener, preservative and prebiotics), and yoghurt (important source of nutrient and carrier of probiotic starter culture *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus*) can be produced with improved shelflife, physicochemical and sensory properties. This study was carried out to isolate and characterization of *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* from commercial milk (fura) hawkers in Maiduguri.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

The sample was obtained locally from commercial milk (fura) hawkers in Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria, stored at -2°C to -4°C, and then transferred to the laboratory for further analysis.

Isolation and characterization of Lactic acid bacteria

Preparation and Isolation of the Bacteria

Media Preparation

De Man Rogosa Sharpe (MRS) medium, supplemented with 100 mg of cycloheximide antibiotic, was used for the isolation of *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* according to the manufacturer's instructions [5].

Isolation Procedure

An aliquot of 0.1 mL milk (fura) was placed on MRS agar plates and incubated at 35°C to 45°C for 72 hours to detect cocci and bacilli. Isolates were selected based on acid production, indicated by a clear zone around the colony on MRS medium. Acid-producing isolates were subcultured on MRS agar and incubated again at 35°C to 45°C for 72 hours.

Biochemical Test for Identification

For further identification and confirmation, isolates were subjected to a series of biochemical tests. These included observing cell and colonial morphology to determine the shape and structure of the colonies. Gram staining was performed to ascertain whether the bacteria were Gram-positive or Gram-negative. The catalase test checked for the

presence of the catalase enzyme, while the oxidase test detected cytochrome c oxidase enzyme. The citrate test assessed the bacteria's ability to use citrate as a carbon source, and the indole test determined the production of indole from tryptophan. The urease test evaluated the ability to hydrolyze urea. Additionally, the MRVP test, which includes Methyl Red and Voges-Proskauer tests, was conducted to analyze fermentation end-products. The motility test observed bacterial movement, and sugar fermentation tests with maltose, glucose, sucrose, and fructose were performed to assess fermentation capabilities. Following these tests, the isolates were stored on MRS agar slants at 4°C for preservation.

DNA extraction from bacteria isolates

DNA extraction was performed using the crude DNA extraction method as described by Anson *et al.* [6]. Isolates were heat-killed at 80°C for one hour, with intermittent vortexing to ensure thorough cell disruption.

PCR Amplification

Duplex PCR was performed using primers specified in the study by Lu *et al.* [7]. Each reaction mixture consisted of 12.5 µL of PCR Master Mix (One Taq Quick-Load Master Mix, NEB M0486L, Inqababiotech SA), 1.5 µL of each primer, and 4.5 µL of template DNA. RNase-free water was added to achieve a total reaction volume of 25 µL. The PCR amplification was conducted in a thermocycler with the following conditions: an initial denaturation at 94°C for 5 minutes, followed by 25 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 30 seconds, annealing at 55°C for 30 seconds, and extension at 72°C for 30 seconds, with a final extension at 72°C for 7 minutes.

The PCR products were separated by electrophoresis on a 1% agarose gel in 1X TAE buffer, run at 6 V/cm for 3 hours. The gel was subsequently stained with ethidium bromide for visualization.

Primers for *Streptococcus thermophilus*

F- LACZ:CACTATGCTCAGAATACA, LACZ

R- LACZ:CGAACAGCATTGATGTTA

Primers for *Lactobacillus delrueckii*

F-DEL: CAACATGAGTCGCATGATTCAAG,

R-DEL:GGAACCACCTCTCTCTGCTGTAG

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Microbiological Analysis

The results from the microbiological analysis of the samples indicate distinct characteristics for different isolates. All tested samples exhibited small, raised colonies with varying colours and textures: creamy, shiny colonies were predominantly associated with *Lactobacillus spp.*, while whitish, round colonies were linked with *Streptococcus spp.* Biochemical tests revealed that all isolates were negative for indole, citrate, urease, MR, and VP tests, but positive for lactose, maltose, glucose, sucrose, and fructose fermentation (Table 1). This pattern suggests that the isolates are consistent with *Lactobacillus spp.* or *Streptococcus spp.*, known for their carbohydrate fermentation profiles. Specifically, the positive results for carbohydrate fermentation across all samples, coupled with consistent colony morphology, help in the identification of these bacterial strains (Table 1).

Table 1: Biochemical Test Results of Lactic Bacteria Isolates

Sample	Growth on MRS	Grams reaction	Indole	Citrate	Urease	MR	VP	Lactose	Maltose	Glucose	Sucrose	Fructose	Isolate
1A	Small,raised,creamy shiny colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus Spp</i>
1B	Small,raised,whitish round colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus Spp</i>
1L	Small,raised,whitish round colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Streptococcus Spp</i>
2A	Small,raised,whitish round colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus Spp</i>
2B	Small,raised,whitish round colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Streptococcus Spp</i>
2S	Small,raised,whitish ,shiny colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Streptococcus Spp</i>
2L	Small round,creamy shiny colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus Spp</i>
3S	Small,whitish round shiny colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Streptococcus Spp</i>
3L	Small,raised,creamy shiny colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus Spp</i>
4L	Small,raised,creamy shiny colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus Spp</i>
4B	Small,raised,creamy shiny colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus Spp</i>
4S	Small,raised,whitish round colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus Spp</i>
5L	Small,raised,creamy shiny colonies	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	<i>Lactobacillus Spp</i>

30 samples of locally hawk milk (Fura) were inoculated on MRS media, and biochemical test media for phenotypic and biochemical reactions based on the Bergys manual of systemic bacteriology. Four (4) out of the fifteen (15) isolates obtained were identified based on biochemical test results as *Streptococcus thermophilus*, 11 out of the isolates were identified as *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*. *Lactobacillus* spp and *Streptococcus* spp were identified and characterization as Lactic acid bacteria associated with traditional fermentation of dairy products [8]. *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* were identified in 87.27% and 94.54% of traditional yoghurt samples in a study to determine the antibiotic resistance profile of indigenous *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* Strains isolated from traditional yoghurt [9].

Figure 1: Genomic DNA Amplification

Polymerase Chain Reaction (Genomic DNA)

Phenotypic and biochemical test are not enough to accurately characterize lactic bacteria from milk samples. It is thus necessary to further perform a molecular testing, to accurately identify the isolates to be used in food production. In this study, a total of 15 isolates from locally fermented milk were subjected to conventional PCR to identify *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*. Three (3) isolates yielded a 1000 bp amplicon indicating *Streptococcus thermophilus*.

Similar study was reported by Anbukkarasi *et al.* [10] who got 74 isolates that yielded the 968-bp amplicon by species-specific PCR using LacZ gene primer. In another study, Lu *et al.* [7] detected three (3) *Streptococcus thermophilus* out of eight traditionally fermented Milk samples. In addition, [7], were able to detect other lactic acid bacteria from the locally fermented milk. these include; *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus Fermentum* and *Lactobacillus helveticus*.

The difference between the isolation rate and the difference in the type of lactic acid producing bacteria isolated from these current study and previous studies may be due to differences in traditional method of local fermentation,

environmental factors and method of identification. Previous studies in Nigeria Evaluated the bacteriological quality of fermented milk. Their results revealed that *Bacillus Spp* and *Streptococci Spp* were amongst the common bacterial isolate from locally fermented milk [11].

The relatively stable count in this study is in agreements with findings of [12] that states; a strong correlation exist between lactic acid bacteria count and pH in symbiotic bioactive yoghurt, when the lactic acid bacteria count increases, the pH of the product decreases. This is also in conformity to the pH values of the control yoghurt samples were pH decreases further as the lactic acid bacteria count increases. Similar Findings in pH decrease in dairy products as a result of increase in counts during storage were reported by [13,14].

CONCLUSION

The microbiological analysis of the locally fermented milk samples revealed a predominance of *Lactobacillus spp.* and *Streptococcus spp.*, with *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* identified as the primary isolates. Biochemical tests confirmed the carbohydrate fermentation patterns typical of these bacteria. The molecular analysis further validated these findings, highlighting that PCR amplification of genomic DNA is essential for precise identification. The presence of these lactic acid bacteria aligns with previous studies on traditional dairy products, emphasizing the importance of microbial profiles in fermentation processes. Variations in bacterial types and counts across studies suggest that traditional fermentation methods, environmental conditions, and identification techniques can influence the microbiological composition of dairy products.

This study recommends the that given the limitations of biochemical tests alone in identifying lactic acid bacteria, incorporating molecular methods like PCR in routine analyses is recommended to ensure accurate strain identification and improve product consistency. To achieve more consistent bacterial profiles in fermented dairy products, standardizing traditional fermentation methods and conditions could help in replicating successful outcomes and reducing variability. Implementing stringent quality control measures in dairy production can ensure that the desired bacterial strains are maintained throughout the fermentation process, improving the final product's safety and efficacy.

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